

An opinion article entitled:
***The Omani public's request for information about
the explosion of wireless pager communication devices in
Lebanon through digital media platforms***

Mohammed Salim Hamood Alsadi- PH.D. student at the Institute de Persse
des Sciences de information- Manouba University in Tunisia

Abstract

As the use of digital technologies in the content industry grows, content production has started to adopt new patterns in conveying current events, as it represents one of the key pillars of the success of news organizations.

In particular, the explosion incident involving the wireless pager communication devices of Hezbollah members occurred because Israel planted explosive charges inside them. The party used these devices to enhance the security of its communications due to concerns about eavesdropping on its calls.

Digital media platforms are known for providing information and news to the public regarding the incident of the explosion of wireless pager communication devices through text, audio, and images.

In addition to helping attract the public's interest and deepen their understanding of the issues that concern them, this leads to the creation of a digital media environment based on interaction, dialogue, and participation between platform operators and the information-seeking audience.

This leads to a higher level of interaction with the content presented, as the audience's behavior in seeking information is shaped by the activities the user undertakes while searching for the necessary information and the information sources that meet their needs.

Keywords: *Information request, Incident of the explosion of wireless communication devices (pagers), Digital Media Platforms*

Introduction:

The internet has become more advanced with the emergence of new interactive visual media that have contributed to the media industry.

Media institutions have turned to creating digital platforms online to leverage technology and its applications in covering topics related to current events.

Digital media has also fostered widespread public engagement and shaped public attitudes toward contemporary issues, due to its transmission of interactive content related to the explosion of Hezbollah's wireless pager communication devices, which resulted in numerous deaths and injuries, presented in text, sound, and image on its digital news platforms.

This contributes to creating an interactive environment based on dialogue and participation, as well as the formation of different opinions and reactions regarding this issue among those responsible for digital media platforms and the audience following them, reflecting the audience's behavior towards seeking information through those platforms. Therefore, we will highlight in our topic : An opinion article entitled: The Omani public's request for information about the explosion of wireless pager communication devices in Lebanon through digital media platforms.

Cognitive framework:

Digital media platforms and the Omani public's seeking of information about the explosion incident of wireless pager communication devices in Lebanon:

They are news platforms through which digital content is delivered to users via interactive media in various forms such as digital images and video clips. Many digital devices can edit, store, and display digital media (Hala Ghraba, 2023, 480).

In the age of digital information, the media plays a pivotal role in providing the public with news and information about current

events. This is especially regarding the incident involving the explosion of wireless pager communication devices in Lebanon, which raised concerns among the Omani public, prompting them to seek accurate and reliable information through digital media platforms (Smith, 2023).

Digital media platforms are one of the media means used to produce content within news organizations in text, audio, and image formats. Their aim is to broadcast content related to current events, particularly topics concerning the explosion of wireless pager communication devices in Lebanon.

The "pager" is a portable wireless device used for sending and receiving short text messages and communications through audio and visual signals transmitted via a dedicated wireless network specifically designed for these services. These devices operate on standard (AAA) batteries or rechargeable lithium batteries that can last for several continuous days (Abdul Fattah Khattab, 2024).

Information-seeking behavior is based on the intentional search and acquisition of specific information by the audience through the selection of various suitable sources. (Varsha Bharadwaj, Javed Khan, 2016).

The social interactions among information seekers are continuous and collaborative throughout the seeking process (Meng et al, 2015, 675).

It can be said that digital applications have assisted communicators in disseminating content and providing users with information across various fields. (Madhusudhan Margam, S. O, 2017).

Digital media platforms have contributed to more interactive roles for the audience regarding the content presented, allowing them to express their opinions through comments and interactive discussions about news stories related to current events that interest them (Nashwa Aql, 2024, 265).

The Importance of Digital Media Platforms:

Digital media platforms are an effective means of conveying information quickly and easily, making them the preferred choice for many. In seeking the latest updates regarding the explosion of pager

devices, the Omani public was eager for accurate details about the incident and its effects, reflecting the urgent need for information in times of crisis. (Al-Harthy, 2023).

Figure (1) illustrates wireless communication devices (the pager)

There are various digital media platforms used to obtain information about the incident of the explosion of Hezbollah's pager wireless communication devices, including:

- 1- (Facebook):** A social network that enables media professionals to contribute to event production, cover them, and comment freely. Moreover, most institutions rely on it to convey their news and programs for promotion and to facilitate direct communication between the institution and its audience. (Mohammed Bounajma, 2024, 76).
- 2- (X Platform):** A social network for virtual interaction among individuals that allows its users to share news and topics and engage in discussions to address problems within the community through interactions via tweets using hashtags #. (Waad Mansour, 2020, 664). The news digital media platforms on

Twitter are official platforms established by official institutions and media at the national level (Zainab Muhammad, 2021, 248).

- 3- **(YouTube):** It is one of the most famous websites for sharing video files that include various topics based on the interests of its viewers (Maha Mukhtar, 2024, 283).
- 4- **(WhatsApp):** An application that enables users to send and share text messages, voice messages, and files across various groups through text, voice, and images, as well as make calls based on their needs. Noha Sabri, 2022, 207).
- 5- **(Instagram):** A social media platform that enables users to upload and digitally filter photos and videos, sharing them through groups (Shaimaa Elhawari, Mahmoud Mohamed, 2022, 234).
- 6- **(Tik Tok):** A social network that allows its users to create short videos and share them with others to attract the largest audience.

There are various topics related to the incident involving the explosion of Hezbollah's pager communication devices on digital media platforms, including:

- 1- Explosive charges were planted in the wireless communication devices (pagers) of Hezbollah by Israel, in collaboration with the manufacturer, by modifying the software of the pagers to trigger an explosion signal upon receiving specific messages accurately.
- 2- Many casualties and injuries.
- 3- Threatening the security and stability of the region.
- 4- Targeting the party's leaders and their communication systems.
- 5- The spread of fear and panic among citizens, along with chaos in the streets, shops, and homes throughout the country.

Interacting with topics related to the incident involving the explosion of Hezbollah's pager wireless communication devices across digital media channels:

This means that the recipient expresses their opinion about the presented content freely, without any censorship (Sherihan Mohamed, 2022, 1298).

It is based on planned efforts in designing digital content aimed at maximizing audience participation in the communication process, through the free selection of content and services according to their needs and interests (Ahmed Sobhi, 2021, 93).

The interaction also represents additional roles that the audience assumes. (Theunissen, Petra, 2018, 49).

The Omani public also showed great interest in the incident by engaging with the content related to it through digital media platforms to understand its causes and potential effects on security. Rumors were also circulated, highlighting the need to verify information before publishing it. (Jones, A 2023).

Forms of interaction with topics related to the incident of the explosion of Hezbollah's wireless pager communication devices through digital media platforms:

It refers to the audience's interaction with the news content presented on digital platforms through liking, commenting, and sharing (Nada Mustafa, Suha Issam, 2024, 577).

There are many forms of interaction with the themes related to the incident of the explosion of Hezbollah's pager communication devices through digital media platforms (Eman Mohamed, 2023, 249), including:

- 1- Liked interaction:** It is a feature that allows the user to subscribe to various digital news pages, whether newspapers or television channels, to follow the latest news related to the content that interests them to interact with through those sites.

- 2- **interact by commenting:** It means dialogue between users about the contents of issues that arouse their interest in the digital news pages that they follow to form different opinions about them, and it also represents one of the most important interactive contributions for the public (Mohamed, 2023, p. 249).
- 3- **Interact by Participation:** This feature allows users to exchange ideas about news material related to issues that interest them and share them from one site to another using text, audio, and images.

The role of traditional and digital media in supplying the Omani public with information:

Despite the rise of digital media, traditional journalism still plays a crucial role in delivering news and information to the public by providing Omani newspapers with comprehensive coverage of current events and offering precise analyses of the situation. (Smith, J. 2023).

The challenges faced by Omani citizens in obtaining accurate information related to current events:

The Omani public has encountered numerous challenges in accessing accurate information regarding current events, as there has been a mix of legitimate news and rumors. This underscores the importance of empowering the public to differentiate between reliable and unreliable sources. (Al-Harthy, 2023).

Conclusion:

It can be said that the incident of the explosion of wireless pager communication devices in Lebanon highlighted the importance of digital news media in times of crises, and the Omani audience should be more conscious of the information sources they rely on in their pursuit of news from reliable sources.

Sources and References:

- Amohamed Bounajma (2024). Shifts in communicative frameworks in the virtual world "Social media applications as a model," a research paper published in the Journal of Media Studies, Germany: Berlin, The Arab Democratic Center, Issue 26, Volume 11, February 2024.

- Abd al-Fattah Khattab (2024). "The Pager": From a Means of Communication to a Tool of Assassination. The magazine's website is available at the following link: <https://www.majalla.com>
- Al-Harthy, M. (2023). Social Media and Public Reaction in Oman: A Case Study of Recent Events. Omani Journal of Social Sciences, 5(2), 34-50.
- Ahmad Sobhi Muhammad Hassan (2021). The Uses of Egyptian Youth of the Live Streaming Feature on "Facebook" and the Gratifications Achieved from It, unpublished master's thesis, Al-Azhar University, Faculty of Media, pp. 93-94.
- Eman Mohamed Ahmed (2023). The role of 'YouTube channels in developing digital education skills, An opinion article published in the Journal of Media Studies, Berlin: The Arab Democratic Center, Issue 22, February 2023 AD,p249.
- Hala Gharabah (2023). Building a Communication Performance Model for Metaverse Applications in Egyptian News Websites, published in the Egyptian Journal of Mass Communication Research, Beni Suef University: Faculty of Media, Issue 2, Volume 5, July 2023.
- Jones, A. (2023). Misinformation in the Digital Age: Challenges and Solutions. International Review of Communication, 29(1), 101-118.
- Maha Mukhtar Hassan (2024). The Egyptian Youth's Quest for Information on Labor Market Skill Development from YouTube as a Tool for Self-Learning, a research published in the Scientific Journal of Journalism Research, Cairo University: Faculty of Mass Communication, Issue 28, Year 2024.

- Mansour Nasser (2020). The Role of Social Media Users: A Case Study of Twitter in Addressing Issues of Domestic Violence Against Women: A Study Conducted with a Sample of Twitter Users in Saudi Society from Both Genders, Unpublished Master's Thesis, Published Research in the Journal of the Faculty of Education, Al-Azhar University, Issue 185, Volume 3, January 2020.
- Meng et al (2015):" The Roles and Interplay of Intragroup Conflict and Team Emotion Management on Information Seeking Behaviors in Team Contexts",Communication Research, Vol. 42(5) 675–700.
- Madhusudhan Margam, S. O. (2017). Mobile information services and initiatives in university libraries: A new way of. ResearchGate. Available at the following link: <https://www.researchgate.net>
- Nada Mustafa Muhammad, Suha Essam Muhammad (2024). The Relationship Between Exposure to News Coverage of the Palestinian Cause on Social Media and Mental Resilience Among University Youth, Research Published in the Egyptian Journal of Media Research, Cairo University: Faculty of Media, Issue 86, January 2024.
- Nashwa Aql (2024). The Semantic Features of User Comments on Social Media Platforms Regarding the Russian-Ukrainian War, a study published in the Scientific Journal of Radio and Television Research, Cairo University: Faculty of Media, Issue 29, July 2024.
- Theunissen, Petra (2018). Philosophy and Ethics of Engagement, in: Johnston, Kim A. and Taylor, Maureen (Editors). The Handbook of Communication Engagement. Wiley-Blackwell. 49.

- Smith, J. (2023). The Role of Digital Media in Crisis Communication. *Journal of Media Studies*, 12(3), 45-67.
- Sherihan Mohamed Tawfiq Abdel Hafiz (2022). *Comments of Users on Egyptian News Pages on Facebook*, A study published in the *Journal of Media Research*, Al-Azhar University, Faculty of Media, Issue 60, Volume 3, January 2022.
- Shimaa Al-Hawari, Mahmoud Mohamed (2022). The Role of Social Media Applications in Raising Youth Awareness of the Dangers of Cyber Extortion, Opinion Article Published in the *Journal of Media Studies*, Germany: Berlin: Democratic Arab Center, Issue 20, Volume 5, August 2022.
- Varsha Bharadwaj, Javed Khan. (2016). INFORMATION SEEKING BEHAVIORS IN ELECTRONIC ENVIRONMENT *International Journal of Research Granthaalayah*, Vol. 4 No. Volume 4 Issue 12 - December, Available at the following link: <https://www.granthaalayahpublication.org>
- Zainab Mohammed Hamid (2021). The Impact of Reliance on Official Saudi Media Platforms on Twitter on Public Knowledge and Behaviors Regarding the COVID-19 Pandemic, Research published in the *Journal of Media Research*, Cairo: Al-Azhar University, Faculty of Media, Issue 57, Volume 1, April 2021.